

METACOGNITION AND ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AMONG THE SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN WEST BENGAL

Swami Vidyamritananda

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Education, Raiganj University, Uttar Dinajpur,
West Bengal, India

Dr. Biswajit Chatterjee (Corresponding Author)

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Raiganj University, Uttar Dinajpur,
West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Metacognition essentially means ‘thinking about one’s own thinking’. Attention, memory, judgment and assessment, reasoning and calculation, problem solving and decision making, and comprehension are all examples of cognitive abilities and processes. The urge to achieve something can be termed as Achievement Motivation, which varies from individual to individual. Over the years, researchers have proven that Metacognition and Achievement Motivation play a key role in the learning outcomes of learners. In the present study, an attempt has been made to measure the Metacognition and Achievement Motivation level of the students studying at the secondary level in the Govt. /Govt.-aided southern districts schools of West Bengal, affiliated with WBBSE. The result revealed that Girl students have a significantly higher level of Metacognition and Achievement Motivation than the boy students. Furthermore, the students from rural schools possess a significantly higher level of Metacognition as well as Achievement Motivation than the urban school students. The research also establishes a statistically significant strong positive correlation between the level of Metacognition and Achievement Motivation of students studying at secondary level schools in West Bengal.

Keywords : Metacognition, Achievement Motivation, Secondary, Correlation

INTRODUCTION

The word ‘metacognition’ was coined by Flavell (1979). The term ‘metacognition’ refers to ‘the individual’s own awareness and consideration of his or her cognitive processes and strategies’. The prefix ‘meta’ (Greek for “after” or “beyond”) denotes something that extends beyond the topic to which it is related. Metacognition essentially means ‘thinking about one’s own thinking’. Attention, memory, judgment and assessment, reasoning and calculation, problem solving and decision making, and comprehension are all examples of cognitive abilities and processes. Metacognitive behavior is very widespread. Students who underwent metacognitive training, including pretesting, self-evaluation, and creating study plans, performed better in the examination (Casselmann & Atwood, 2017).

Multiple studies have explored the relationship between metacognition and academic achievement in various domains. In a study on the development of metacognitive thinking skills, researchers found that the ability to follow and regulate cognitive processes, such as learning, problem-solving, and reasoning, was directly linked to improved performance in professional settings. (Tuncer & Kaysi, 2013) Similarly, a review of the literature on metacognitive teaching strategies revealed that specific instructional practices aimed at enhancing students' metacognitive capacities can have a significant impact on their academic achievement. (Ellis et al., 2014)

The urge to achieve something can be termed as Achievement Motivation, which varies from individual to individual. Achievement motivation, according to Rabideau (2005), is defined as the desire to succeed or achieve excellence by satisfying one's needs through a variety of methods, motivated by both internal and external factors. The degree to which people with high achievement motivation engage in achievement-oriented behavior is influenced by characteristics such as race, environment, child-rearing techniques, employment status, climate, and family structure (Bidyadhar, 2006).

Numerous studies have been conducted that exhibit the role of Achievement Motivation in academic achievement. Some notable studies are mentioned here. Tyagi, (2014) conducted a study on 'Achievement motivation learning style parental involvement as correlates of academic achievement of the secondary school students'. The study examined the interrelationships among learning style, achievement motivation, parental involvement, and academic achievement. Findings revealed that learning style has a direct and significant positive correlation with academic achievement, as well as with achievement motivation and parental involvement. Sunita (2020) conducted a Study on the Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students about their Achievement Motivation, Intelligence and self-efficacy. The descriptive survey study investigated the influence of psychological factors—achievement motivation, intelligence, and self-efficacy — on academic achievement among senior secondary students in Haryana. Findings revealed significant differences in academic achievement, favouring female students and those from private schools. Achievement motivation, intelligence, and self-efficacy were found to be positively correlated with academic success, with notable variations across gender and school type.

In the present study, an attempt has been made to understand the level of Metacognition and Achievement Motivation among the secondary school students studying in the Govt. aided (WB) schools affiliated to the West Bengal Board of Secondary Education (WBBSE) and located in the southern districts of West Bengal. This study also focused on finding out the differences, if they exist, within two demographic variables, namely Location and gender, about the level of students' Metacognition and Achievement Motivation. The study also aimed to reveal the level of correlation between students' Metacognition and Achievement Motivation.

OBJECTIVES

- O₁ : To study the level of Metacognition of students at secondary level across the location of schools and gender of the students.

- O₂ : To study the level of Achievement Motivation of students at secondary level across the location of schools and the gender of the students.
- O₃ : To compare the level of Metacognition of secondary school students across the location of schools and gender of the students.
- O₄ : To compare the level of Achievement Motivation of secondary school students across the location of schools and gender of the students.
- O₅ : To find out the relationships between the level of Metacognition and Achievement Motivation of students studying at secondary level.

HYPOTHESES

- H₀₁ : There is no significant difference between urban and rural students studying at secondary level in their level of Metacognition.
- H₀₂ : There is no significant difference between boy and girl students studying at secondary level in their level of Metacognition.
- H₀₃ : There is no significant difference in Achievement Motivation between urban and rural students at studying secondary level.
- H₀₄ : There is no significant difference in Achievement Motivation between boy and girl students studying at secondary level.
- H₀₅ : There is no significant correlation between Metacognition and Achievement Motivation of students studying at secondary level.

METHODOLOGY

The research followed a descriptive survey method. The English to Bengali translation of the two Standardized scales are conducted. For the systematic adoption of these two translated scales, experts' validation and reliability checks were performed. Then the scales were administered to randomly selected students of five strata-wise randomly selected WBBSE schools. The data gathered from the scales were entered into MS Excel. Finally, SPSS (Version 29.0) software is used for analysis of the data.

Variables

Two major variables are considered for the study: Metacognition and Achievement Motivation. To study the effect of these two major variables on the population demography, two categorical variables, Location of Schools (Urban and Rural) and Gender of Students (Boy and Girl), were chosen.

Population

For this research work, the population is Ninth standard (Class IX) students from Govt/ Govt.-aided schools situated in the southern districts of West Bengal and affiliated to the West Bengal Board of Secondary Education (WBBSE). Five schools from five districts of West Bengal were selected for this study, namely – Howrah, Hooghly, Kolkata, Purba Midnapore and Bankura.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

A stratified random sampling procedure was adopted by the researcher for the study.

Categories	Urban	Rural	Total
Boy	40	29	69
Girl	20	31	51
Total	60	60	120

Tools of the Study

- Singh-Bali Metacognition Scale (SBMCS) by Prof. (Dr.) Mubarak Singh and Ms. Ana Bali (2018). There are 50 'Likert Type Scale' items in the questionnaires. Each scale item contains 5 MCQ-based questions – Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The scale is a 5-point scale, and responses are given weightage from 5 to 1.
- Deo-Mohan Achievement Motivation Scale [DMAMS] (n-Ach / n-Achievement) by Prof. Prathibha Deo and Dr. Asha Mohan (2011 revised). The Test scale contains 50 multiple-choice-based questions, out of which 37 were positive items and 13 were negative items. Respondent needs to choose from five alternate options, viz. Always, Frequently, Sometimes, Rarely and Never.

The originals of both the Scales are written in the English language. Therefore, for administering the Scales in Bengali medium schools, English to Bengali translations are made by the researcher. The English to Bengali translation of both the Scales was validated by 3 experts. Necessary modifications of the Scales are incorporated after taking into consideration the suggestions made by the tool validators. Both English and Bengali versions are then administered on a group of 60 students in one-month interval to test the equality of both forms of the scales. A significant strong correlation ($r = 0.558$) was found at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) between the English and Bengali versions of SBMCS (2018). For DMAMS (2011 revised), the correlation coefficient was found to be significantly strong ($r = 0.622$) at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) between the English and Bengali versions.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The schools selected for this study were not selected with strict randomization. The stratified random sampling method was followed.
- The schools were selected from the southern districts of West Bengal.
- The numbers of schools were only five; it might be increased by taking more schools under the study.
- The sample of this study was selected only from the Govt. / Govt. aided Bengali medium schools affiliated to the WBBSE. Private schools, English Medium Schools and schools affiliated to other Boards like CBSE, ICSE, etc. have been kept out of this present study.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Data related to this study were collected by the researcher through administering the translated standardized tools. A booklet containing both the scales was printed. The printed booklets were then sent by post to the Head teachers of randomly selected schools based on their strata and location in five districts of West Bengal that were selected for the study.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Metacognition level of secondary students measured by SBMCS		
Categories	Statistic	Std. Error
Mean	197.19	1.797
Median	201.00	
Variance	387.702	
Std. Deviation	19.690	
Skewness	-.412	.221
Kurtosis	-.639	.438

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Achievement Motivation level of secondary students measured by DMAMS		
Categories	Statistic	Std. Error
Mean	142.08	2.188
Median	146.50	
Variance	574.507	
Std. Deviation	23.969	
Skewness	-.352	.221
Kurtosis	-.766	.438

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Objective-wise Analysis of Data

Table 4: Group Statistics for Metacognition Location of Schools

Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Urban	60	192.78	17.447
Rural	60	201.60	20.929

Table 5: Group Statistics for Metacognition - Gender of students

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Boy	69	192.90	19.110
Girl	51	203.00	19.137

Table 6: Group Statistics for Achievement Motivation - Location of Schools

Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Urban	60	137.07	21.2957
Rural	60	147.08	25.5788

Table 7: Group Statistics for Achievement Motivation - Gender of students

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Boy	69	136.55	24.1675
Girl	51	149.55	21.775

O₃: To compare the level of Metacognition of secondary school students across the location of schools and gender of the students.

Testing of H₀1: There is no significant difference between urban and rural students studying at secondary level in their level of Metacognition.

Table 8: Group Statistics and Independent Samples t-Test for Level of Metacognition - Location of Schools							
Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. (Two-Sided) p
Urban	60	192.78	17.447	2.252	-2.506**	118	0.014
Rural	60	201.60	20.929	2.702			
(** Significant at the 0.05 level)							

Interpretation

From the analysis in **Table 8**, it is found that in comparing students' Metacognition level between urban and rural schools at the secondary level, the calculated $t_{(118)}$ value is 2.506 and 'p' value is 0.014 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, 't' is significant at the 0.05 level. So, **H₀1** is rejected, and it can be safely said that urban School students are significantly different from rural School students concerning their Metacognition.

Testing of H₀2: There is no significant difference between boy and girl students studying at secondary level in their level of Metacognition.

Table 9 : Group Statistics and Independent Samples t-Test for the Level of Metacognition - Gender of Students							
Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. (Two-Sided) p
Boy	69	192.00	19.110	2.301	2.861**	118	0.005
Girl	51	203.00	19.137	2.680			
(** Significant at the 0.05 level)							

Interpretation

From the analysis in **Table 9**, it is found that in comparing students' Metacognition level between boy and girl students at the secondary level, the calculated $t_{(118)}$ value is 2.861 and 'p' value is 0.005 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, 't' is significant at the 0.05 level. So, **H₀2** is rejected, and it can be safely said that secondary boy students are significantly different from secondary girl students concerning their Metacognition.

O₄ : To compare the level of Achievement Motivation of secondary school students across the location of schools and gender of the students.

Testing of H₀₃ : There is no significant difference in Achievement Motivation between urban and rural students at studying secondary level.

Table 10: Group Statistics and Independent Samples t-Test for Level of Achievement Motivation - Gender of Students							
Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. (Two-Sided) p
Urban	60	137.07	21.295	2.749	-2.331**	118	0.021
Rural	60	147.08	25.578	3.302			
(** Significant at the 0.05 level)							

Interpretation

From the analysis in **Table 10**, it is found that in comparing students' Achievement Motivation level between urban and rural students at the secondary level, the calculated $t_{(118)}$ value is 2.331 and 'p' value is 0.021 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, 't' is significant at the 0.05 level. So, **H₀₃** is rejected, and it can be safely said that urban secondary school students are significantly different from rural secondary school students concerning their Achievement Motivation.

Testing of H₀₄ : There is no significant difference in Achievement Motivation between boy and girl students studying at secondary level.

Table 11: Group Statistics and Independent Samples t-Test for Level of Achievement Motivation - Location of Schools							
Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. (Two-Sided) p
Boy	69	136.55	24.167	2.909	3.036**	118	0.003
Girl	51	149.55	21.770	3.048			
(** Significant at the 0.05 level)							

Interpretation

From the analysis in **Table 11**, it is found that in comparing students' Achievement Motivation level between boy and girl students at the secondary level, the calculated $t_{(118)}$ value is 3.036 and 'p' value is 0.003 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, 't' is significant at the 0.05 level. So, **H₀₄** is rejected, and it can be safely said that secondary boy students are significantly different from secondary girl students concerning their Achievement Motivation.

O_5 : To find out the relationships between the level of Metacognition and Achievement Motivation of students studying at secondary level.

Testing of H_05 : There is no significant correlation between Metacognition and Achievement Motivation of students studying at secondary level.

Table 12 : Correlations between Metacognition and Achievement Motivation			
		SBMCS	DMAMS (n-Ach)
SBMCS	Pearson Correlation	1	0.656**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<0.001
	N	120	120
DMAMS (n-Ach)	Pearson Correlation	0.656**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	
	N	120	120
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)			

Interpretation

The analysis in **Table 12** shows that, correlation coefficient, i.e. 'r', between the students' score of Metacognition and Achievement Motivation is 0.656, and the 'p' value is less than 0.001 ($p < 0.05$), which is significant at the 0.05 level. Hence, H_05 is rejected. So, it can be interpreted that there exists a strong positive correlation between the level of Metacognition and Achievement Motivation of students studying at secondary level.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

While finding the difference in the level of Metacognition between the Urban and Rural students studying in secondary schools, it has been found that the rural school students possess a significantly higher level of Metacognition than the urban school students. Whereas, the study reveals that girl students have a significantly higher level of Metacognition than the boy students. Tiwana (2019) performed similar studies in Haryana, India. The study also finds that female students' Metacognition level is superior to that of male students at the senior secondary level. But, rural and urban student were found to be similar in terms of their level of Metacognition.

While comparing the difference in the level of Achievement Motivation between the Urban and Rural students studying at secondary level, a similar outcome has been observed in the study. That means the rural school students possess a significantly higher level of Achievement Motivation than the urban school students, and the girl students have a significantly higher level of Achievement Motivation than the boy students. The study of Sunit (2020) also confirms that female students have significantly higher Achievement Motivation than male students at the senior secondary level.

The research also establishes a statistically significant strong positive correlation between the level of Metacognition and Achievement Motivation of students studying at secondary level

schools in West Bengal. The study of Tiwana (2019) conducted in Haryana also indicates a similar significant and positive correlation between Metacognition and Academic Achievement of senior secondary school students. This suggests that students who exhibit a higher level of Metacognition also tend to show greater Achievement Motivation in their pursuit of the subjects of their study. In practical terms, students who are more capable of planning, monitoring, and evaluating their learning processes tend to be more driven and motivated to achieve academic success. These findings suggest that fostering metacognitive skills may be an effective strategy for enhancing students' academic motivation.

CONCLUSION

Overall, from the study, it is clear that girl students at the secondary stage have a higher level of Metacognition and Achievement Motivation. Although the recently published WBBSE (West Bengal Board of Secondary Education) Madhyamik Examination Result 2025 reflect a different outcome where boys (Passing percentage: 89.19%) outperformed girls (Passing percentage: 84.31%) with a higher pass percentage. This trend has also been observed in the last few years, where boys outperformed girls with a slightly higher pass percentage. This suggests that apart from Metacognition and achievement motivation, there must be some other associated intervening factors that influence the outcome of the Madhyamik Examination result, which attracts further research on the topic.

REFERENCES

- Bidyadhar, S. (2006). Achievement Motivation among Secondary School Tribal and Non-Tribal Students. *Journal of Indian Education*, 32(1), 108–116.
- Casselmann, B. L., & Atwood, C. H. (2017). Improving General Chemistry Course Performance through Online Homework-Based Metacognitive Training. *J. Chem. Educ.*, 94(12), 1811–1821. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.7b00298>
- Education, T. (2025, May 2). WBBSE Madhyamik Class 10 Toppers 2025: Adrita Sarkar tops with 99.43% marks. *The Times of India*. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/education/news/wbbse-madhyamik-class-10-toppers-2025-adrita-sarkar-tops-with-99-43-marks/articleshow/120811047.cms>
- Ellis, A. K., Denton, D. W., & Bond, J. (2014). An Analysis of Research on Metacognitive Teaching Strategies. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 116, 4015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.883>
- Flavell, J. H. (1979). Metacognition and cognitive monitoring: A new area of cognitive-developmental inquiry. *American Psychologist*, 34(10), 906–911. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066x.34.10.906>
- Huang, C., & Zheng, Q. (2022). How teaching style influences learning effectiveness through learning motivation. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147-4478), 11(6), 468. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v11i6.1933>

- Rabideau, S. T. (2005). *Effects of achievement motivation on behaviour*. <http://www.personalityresearch.org/papers/rabideau.html>
- Sunita. (2020). *A study of academic achievement of senior secondary school students in relation to their achievement motivation, intelligence and self efficacy* [Doctoral Thesis, Baba Mastnath University]. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/570512>
- Tiwana, N. (2019). *Metacognition science self efficacy and learning styles as correlates of students' achievement in science* [Doctoral Thesis, Kurukshetra University]. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/278714>
- Tuncer, M., & Kaysi, F. (2013). The Development of the Metacognitive Thinking Skills Scale. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 3(2), 70. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijld.v3i2.3449>
- Tyagi, S. (2014). *Achievement motivation learning style parental involvement as correlates of academic achievement of the secondary school students* [Doctoral Thesis, Maharshi Dayanand University]. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/107062>